

Data Availability

Low-cost polymers for 3D printing of cardiac anatomical models: pilot test

This supplementary material presents the researchers' qualitative evaluation of the printed models.

Choosing the 3D Model

The 3D model chosen for this study was selected from the website <https://www.thingiverse.com/thing:932606/files>

Explanation of the development of the qualitative assessment instrument

The developed scale is composed of four dimensions (Galati et al., 2019; Okarma et al., 2020; Schlegel et al., 2022)::

- 1 Ease of printing: Ease of use of the printer, considering the number of adjustments in each printer's printing software and the initialization and finalization procedures.
- 2 Object handling: Considers the pleasant feel of the object when handled, as well as its robustness.
- 3 Quality of the object's details: Clear tactile and visual characteristics of the object, with minimal deformation or inaccuracies resulting from printing.
- 4 Material: Ease of purchase in the local market and cost per spool (1 kg) or bottle (1 kg).

The qualitative assessment was carried out using a five-point Likert scale (Trentini, A. et al., 2012):

- 1 = awful
- 2 = bad
- 3 = average
- 4 = good
- 5 = excellent

Qualitative assessment instrument

Dimension 1- Ease of printing		
Item	Description	Scale
1.1	The material is easy to configure in the printer software.	1 = awful 2 = bad 3 = average 4 = good 5 = excellent
1.2	The printing process requires no frequent adjustments.	1 = awful 2 = bad 3 = average 4 = good

		5 = excellent
1.3	The initialization and completion of printing are simple	1 = awful 2 = bad 3 = average 4 = good 5 = excellent
Dimension 2- Object handling		
2.1	The object feels pleasant and uniform to the touch.	1 = awful 2 = bad 3 = average 4 = good 5 = excellent
2.2	The object is durable and does not deform easily.	1 = awful 2 = bad 3 = average 4 = good 5 = excellent
Dimension 3-Quality of the object's details		
3.1	The visual characteristics (shapes, edges, reliefs) are sharp and well-defined.	1 = awful 2 = bad 3 = average 4 = good 5 = excellent
3.2	There is little or no noticeable deformation resulting from printing.	1 = awful 2 = bad 3 = average 4 = good 5 = excellent
3.3	The surface texture is regular and has a good finish.	1 = awful 2 = bad 3 = average 4 = good 5 = excellent
Dimension 4- Material		
4.1	The material is easily found in the local market.	1 = awful 2 = bad 3 = average 4 = good 5 = excellent

4.2	The cost of the material is reasonable compared to its quality.	1 = awful 2 = bad 3 = average 4 = good 5 = excellent
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Printed Models

Tables

Table 1. Average of 3D print quality dimensions analyzed by evaluator A

Aspect evaluated	PLA score*	TPU score *	Resin score *
Dimensão 1- Printing	excellent	good	average
Dimensão 2- Handling	good	excellent	average
Dimensão 3- Quality	excellent	average	excellent
Dimensão 4- Cost	excellent	good	bad

* Aspects were classified as excellent; good; average; bad; awful

Table 2. Average of 3D print quality dimensions analyzed by evaluator B

Aspect evaluated	PLA score *	TPU score *	Resin score *
Dimensão 1- Printing	excellent	average	bad
Dimensão 2- Handling	excellent	excellent	average
Dimensão 3- Quality	excellent	average	excellent
Dimensão 4- Cost	excellent	good	average

* Aspects were classified as excellent; good; average; bad; awful

References:

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